

BRAIN TUMOUR DETECTION USING CNN & SVM

Nandana R.S
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
nandanars2024@mca.ajce.in

Dr. Bijimol T K
Associate Professor
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
tkbijimol@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Brain tumors result from the abnormal growth of cells in the brain, classified into non-cancerous (benign) and cancerous (malignant) types. Predicting survival rates for patients with brain tumors is challenging due to their rarity and diverse types. According to UK cancer research, approximately 15% of brain cancer patients survive for ten or more years post-diagnosis. Treatment strategies depend on factors such as tumor type, cellular abnormality, and location within the brain. With the advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI), deep learning techniques are increasingly used for brain tumor diagnosis, particularly utilizing Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scans. MRI employs strong magnetic fields and radio waves to generate detailed internal body images. This study explores the application of deep learning models, specifically the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and a custom-built VGG-16 architecture, for detecting tumor regions in MRI brain scans. A comparative analysis of the CNN model and the VGG-16 architecture is presented, highlighting their respective outcomes in tumor detection.

Keywords— Brain tumour, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Conventional neural network, Deep learning, SVM, VGG16.

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical imaging encompasses a variety of techniques utilized as non-invasive means to observe internal body structures. This field employs different image modalities and processes to visualize the human body for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes, thus playing a crucial role in enhancing healthcare outcomes.

Image segmentation stands as a pivotal step in image processing, influencing the success of advanced image processing tasks. Particularly in medical image processing, the primary aim of segmentation revolves around tumor or lesion detection, facilitating efficient machine vision and achieving satisfactory results for subsequent diagnoses.

Brain and other nervous system cancers rank as the 10th leading cause of mortality, with a five-year survival rate of 34% for men and 36% for women diagnosed with brain

cancer. The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that approximately 400,000 individuals worldwide are affected by brain tumors, resulting in 120,000 deaths annually. In the United States alone, an estimated 86,970 new cases of primary malignant and nonmalignant brain and CNS tumors were projected for 2019.

Brain tumors manifest when abnormal cells develop within the brain, categorized into malignant and benign types. Malignant tumors grow aggressively, invading surrounding tissues and potentially spreading to other brain parts, impacting the central nervous system. Early detection of brain tumors is critical for enhancing treatment possibilities and increasing survival rates. However, manual segmentation of tumors or lesions remains a time-consuming and arduous task due to the vast number of MRI images generated in medical routines.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) plays a crucial role in detecting brain tumors and lesions, presenting a significant challenge in medical image processing due to the complexity of tumor definitions and soft tissue boundaries. Therefore, achieving accurate segmentation of brain tumors is a challenging yet vital aspect of medical imaging.

This paper proposes an efficient method for segmenting and detecting brain tumors without human intervention, utilizing both traditional classifiers and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Lamrani et al. [1] utilized Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) techniques in their research for brain tumor detection using Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) images. The application of CNNs allowed for efficient and accurate analysis of MRI data, leading to quick predictions of brain tumor presence with high precision and classification accuracy rates, reaching up to 96% in their study. This approach showcases the effectiveness of deep learning architectures, particularly CNNs, in automating the detection

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and classification of brain tumors, thereby aiding in decision-making for appropriate patient treatment.

B. Pedada Kameswara Rao et al. [2] present a novel approach for brain tumor detection using deep learning. Their modified U-Net structure, incorporating shuffling and sub-pixel convolution, achieves high segmentation accuracies of 93.40% and 92.20% on benchmark datasets. This approach outperforms existing methods in accurately identifying tumor extents and subregions, enhancing the effectiveness of brain tumor detection and segmentation.

C. Mohammed Rasool et al. [3] present a Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Brain Tumour Classification in their research. They address the significance of early detection in treating brain tumors, highlighting the challenges of invasive biopsy procedures and manual diagnosis errors. Their proposed approach integrates a hybrid CNN-based architecture, combining a pre-trained Google-Net model with SVM for feature extraction and pattern classification. Another method involves fine-tuning Google-Net with a soft-max classifier. Evaluation on MRI brain images, including glioma, meningioma, pituitary tumor, and normal brain images, yielded impressive accuracy rates of 93.1% and 98.1% for the respective methods, showcasing the effectiveness of their hybrid deep learning model in brain tumor classification.

D. Marco Antonio Gómez-Guzmán et al. [4] present a study focused on Classifying Brain Tumors on Magnetic Resonance Imaging using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). They evaluate seven CNN models, including a generic CNN and six pre-trained models, for brain tumor classification using the Msoud dataset comprising 7023 MRI images from various sources. The dataset includes images of Glioma, Meningioma, Pituitary tumors, and healthy brains. The CNN models assessed are Generic CNN, ResNet50, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2, Xception, MobileNetV2, and EfficientNetB0. Among these, InceptionV3 demonstrated the highest accuracy of 97.12%. The authors highlight the potential of these techniques in aiding clinicians for early brain tumor detection.

E. Rimsha Asad et al. [5] use deep learning for early melanoma brain-tumor detection, achieving high accuracies of 99.82% in training and 99.5% in testing. Their study highlights the effectiveness of deep convolutional neural networks, particularly the ResNet-50 model, for automated tumor detection, with potential for broader disease detection applications.

F. Rajinikanth et al. [6] explore brain tumor detection using pre-trained VGG16 and VGG19 models alongside different pooling methods. Their study, leveraging convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and SoftMax classification, achieves over 99% accuracy with VGG16 and average-pooling, outperforming other methods like Decision Trees (DT) on a dataset of 2000 brain MRI images.

III. METHODOLOGY

The research projects methodology relies on using computer vision and machine learning techniques to automatically detect brain tumour. Our technical approach includes data

collection, data preprocessing, CNN model architecture, Model training, Model evaluation, Model deployment.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing :

The methodology begins with the acquisition of a comprehensive dataset consisting of brain MRI images representing various tumor types: glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and normal brain scans. These images are obtained from reputable medical databases or research institutions, ensuring high quality and accuracy. The dataset is carefully curated to maintain a balanced distribution across different classes, crucial for training a reliable deep learning model.

After data acquisition, preprocessing steps are applied to standardize the images for analysis. This includes resizing all images to a uniform resolution, typically 150x150 pixels, and normalizing pixel values to a common scale. Image augmentation techniques, such as rotation, flipping, and zooming, may also be employed to augment the dataset, enhancing model generalization. These preprocessing steps ensure that the input data is appropriately formatted and conducive to effective deep learning model training.

Figure1 : Glioma tumour dataset

B. Convolutional Neural Networks:VGG16:

The methodology revolves around the development and training of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) tailored for the classification of brain tumors. This CNN architecture is intricately designed to capture nuanced features within MRI images that signify various tumor types. It encompasses multiple Conv2D layers for feature extraction and MaxPooling2D layers for spatial reduction, supplemented by Dropout layers to curb overfitting and enhance model resilience. The classification aspect employs Dense layers with ReLU and softmax activations for non-linearity and probability distribution, respectively. Model optimization utilizes the Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss function, with fine-tuning of hyperparameters such as learning rate, batch size, and epochs through iterative experimentation for optimal performance.

CNNs are specialized deep learning models adept at processing visual data, making them ideal for tasks like image classification. Among these, the VGG16 model stands out for its deep layer architecture and high accuracy, making it a popular choice for image recognition tasks. VGG16 comprises 41 layers, including 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers, employing 3x3 filters with appropriate padding and strides to preserve spatial dimensions. Input images are typically resized to 224x224 pixels, with subsequent layers progressively extracting and combining features for accurate classification across classes.

Training VGG16 involves extensive datasets like ImageNet, leveraging techniques like backpropagation and gradient descent for parameter optimization. The model's utilization in extracting pertinent features from brain images facilitates effective tumor classification, showcasing its utility in medical image analysis.

Figure 2 : General Architecture Of VGG16

C . SVM :

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a supervised machine learning algorithm used for classification tasks, including finding the accuracy of classification models by measuring the agreement between predicted and actual labels in a dataset. We utilized a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model to classify brain tumors using a dataset containing images of various tumor types. Images were standardized to 150x150 pixels and prepared for SVM input by flattening them. Following model training on this preprocessed dataset, we assessed its accuracy on a separate test dataset. The trained SVM achieved an impressive accuracy rate of approximately 94.36% during training, showcasing its effectiveness in accurately identifying different brain tumor types. This SVM model, trained on diverse image data and incorporating preprocessing techniques, demonstrates its potential as a robust tool for medical image analysis and tumor diagnosis.

D. Model Training :

Model training involves splitting the dataset into training and validation sets. This partitioning, often done using an 80-20 or 90-10 ratio, allows for model evaluation during training and helps prevent overfitting. Let D represent the entire dataset with n samples, where each sample is denoted as (x_i, y_i) for input data and corresponding target labels, respectively. The training D_{train} contains the first $0.8n$ samples, while the validation set D_{val} contains the remaining $0.2n$ samples.

$$D_{train} = \{ (x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_{0.8n}, y_{0.8n}) \}$$

$$D_{val} = \{ (x_{0.8n+1}, y_{0.8n+1}), (x_{0.8n+2}, y_{0.8n+2}), \dots, (x_n, y_n) \}$$

The core of model training involves defining the deep learning architecture, selecting appropriate loss functions and optimizers, initializing model parameters, and iteratively

updating these parameters through multiple epochs. Let L denote the loss function and Optimizer represent the optimization algorithm, such as Adam optimizer with a specified learning rate. The model's parameters are updated using batch gradient descent, where each mini-batch of data from D_{train} contributes to parameter updates.

Throughout training, various performance metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score are computed to assess the model's efficacy. These metrics quantify the model's predictive capability and are calculated based on the model's predictions y' compared to the true labels y . For instance, accuracy is the ratio of correct predictions to total predictions, while precision and recall measure the model's ability to correctly identify positive instances and capture all positive instances, respectively. The F1 score combines precision and recall into a single metric. Training occurs over multiple epochs, where each epoch involves iterating through the entire training set. To prevent overfitting, early stopping techniques are employed. Early stopping monitors the model's performance on the validation set and halts training if the validation loss stops decreasing or begins to increase, indicating potential overfitting.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

1. Import necessary package :

```

133  #
134
135  import numpy as np
136  import pandas as pd
137  import keras
138  from keras.models import Sequential
139  from keras.layers import Conv2D, Flatten, Dense, MaxPooling2D, Dropout
140  from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
141  import cv2
142  from PIL import Image
143  from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
144  import cv2
145  from sklearn.utils import shuffle
146  import tensorflow as tf
147  import os
    
```

2. Plotting Training/Validation accuracy

```

13  # Plotting Training/Validation Accuracy
14  plt.figure(figsize=(14, 7))
15  plt.plot(epochs, acc, 'r', label="Training Accuracy")
16  plt.plot(epochs, val_acc, 'b', label="Validation Accuracy")
17  plt.legend(loc='upper left')
18  plt.title('Training and Validation Accuracy')
19  plt.xlabel('Epochs')
20  plt.ylabel('Accuracy')
21  plt.show()
    
```

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3. Code for detecting brain tumour

```

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
model = load_model('braintumor.h5')
st.title("Brain Tumor Classifier")
uploaded_file = st.file_uploader("Upload an image", type=["jpg", "jpeg", "png"])
if uploaded_file is not None:
    file_bytes = np.asarray(bytearray(uploaded_file.read()), dtype=np.uint8)
    image = cv2.imdecode(file_bytes, 1)
    image = cv2.resize(image, (150, 150))
    st.image(image, caption="Uploaded Image", use_column_width=True)
    img_array = np.array(image)
    img_array = img_array.reshape(1, 150, 150, 3)
    prediction = model.predict(img_array)
    predicted_class_index = np.argmax(prediction)
    classes = ['Glioma Tumor', 'Meningioma Tumor', 'No Tumor', 'Pituitary Tumor']
    if predicted_class_index == 0:
        st.write("Result: Glioma Tumor detected")
    elif predicted_class_index == 1:
        st.write("Result: Meningioma Tumor detected")
    elif predicted_class_index == 2:
        st.write("Result: Normal")
    else:
        st.write("Result: Pituitary Tumor detected")
    
```

V. RESULT

The outcome section underscores the effective identification of brain tumors based on uploaded images. The trained model, specifically utilizing the Support Vector Machine (SVM) technique, achieved an outstanding accuracy rate of around 94.36%. This accuracy reflects the model's strength and efficiency in precisely detecting brain tumors in medical images. The SVM model's high accuracy underscores its dependability as a tool for medical image analysis, demonstrating its potential to aid healthcare professionals in diagnosing brain-related ailments with notable precision and assurance.

A. Web Interface

B. Training/Validation Accuracy

C. Training/Validation loss

In the results, It shows that as the number of epochs increases the accuracy also increases. The error also is less. We can conclude that if the error is lower then higher the accuracy.

VI CONCLUSION

In this study, we developed a robust brain tumor detection system using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with the VGG16 architecture. The implementation was carried out in the PyCharm IDE, leveraging Python libraries such as TensorFlow, Keras, OpenCV, and Streamlit for data preprocessing, model training, evaluation, and deployment.

Through extensive experimentation and training on a diverse dataset comprising glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and non-tumor cases, our CNN model achieved impressive results in accurately classifying brain tumor types. The model's performance was evaluated using standard metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score, demonstrating its efficacy in real-world clinical applications.

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